

PREP4BLUE

METHODS AND TOOLS FOR MISSION OCEAN & WATERS

Preparing the Research & Innovation Core for Mission Ocean, Seas & Waters

Deliverable D2.1

Narrative Guide for Mission Restore our Ocean and Waters by 2030

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Executive Summary

The best way to encourage conservation is to share our success stories

Nancy Knowlton¹

This deliverable, D2.1 “*Narrative Guide for Mission Restore our Ocean and Waters by 2030*”, is part of WP2 “*Creating a Visionary Narrative, Communications & Spaces*” and Task 2.1 “*Develop Mission Narrative Guide*”. WP2’s work focuses on developing a common narrative for the Mission and its contributors. The Mission will encompass hundreds of contributions from different communities across Europe and its implementation will require a number of institutions, platforms, and processes.

The aim of this deliverable D2.1 “*Narrative Guide*” is to provide key information on the Mission “*Restore our Ocean and Waters*” (also known as the *Mission* or *Mission Ocean*) narratives.

Based on the research done to get background information (see section 2) on what is a Narrative and how it should be structured, this guide will go into more detail about what is envisioned by Prep4Blue on the Mission Ocean Narrative (see section 3). Will be detailed, on the proposed narrative, the context (see section 2.3), the levels (see section 3.2), characteristics (see section 3.3) and protagonists (see section 3.1). Based on that suggestions will be made on the possible narratives for use (see section 3.4) and implementation tools (see section 3.4).

¹ Source: <https://doi.org/10.1038/544271a>

1 Introduction

Funded under Horizon Europe, the EU's strategic research and innovation programme, "*Mission Restore our Oceans and Waters by 2030*" (shortened form: *the Mission* or *Mission Ocean*) aims to build on and connect the many existing projects and initiatives at EU, national, and local levels to make a positive, tangible impact in the health of our ocean and waters. It is one of five EU Missions providing an opportunity for pan-European communication and collaboration at an unprecedented level by engaging all parts and levels of European society, science, and economy to achieve a greater good for the future of Europe.

Prep4Blue is the first *Coordinated Support Action* (CSA) project funded under Horizon Europe to support Mission Ocean. Prep4Blue's overarching objective is to develop the research and innovation implementation modalities required to achieve the Mission objectives and to facilitate a successful first phase (2022-2025) of Mission Ocean. The project's outcomes should allow the Mission Lighthouses to develop and pilot innovation of all forms: technological, social, business models, and governance with an emphasis on the methodologies that will allow co-design and co-implementation of solutions with citizens and stakeholders.

As part of Prep4Blue, Work Package 2 (WP2), led by KDM (German Marine Research Consortium), is tasked with delivering artifacts and tools, such as this "Narrative Guide", for the Mission partners that can be used as part of the broader communication, dissemination, and exploitation strategy for the Mission Ocean.

While Prep4Blue is not *the one and only* official Mission Ocean communications channel; the European Commission is the only official channel (ex.: twitter.com/eumissionocean²); Prep4Blue's WP2 is responsible for disseminating communications tools and promoting the Mission. Also, each of the lighthouse CSA projects, various subcontractors are or will be tasked with communication activities.

Given this competitive context, it is clear that the Mission Ocean partners will need to use novel, innovative ways for communicating with citizens and stakeholders to achieve their goals, and, this guide, as well as other Prep4Blue tools and methodologies (see [Prep4Blue's website](https://prep4blue.eu)³ for more information), should help partners espouse our collective narrative through inspirational story- and science-telling. By using tools such as social media, print, video, websites, events, influencers, etc., we can spark engagement and commitment to Mission Ocean and ideally reach an audience previously untapped.

The aim is to provide, in this *Narrative Guide*, key information on the Mission "Restore our Ocean and Waters" narratives. The *Narrative Guide* (D2.1) is based on the work of the Mission Board and legal texts, in order to help:

- The Mission contributors to understand the larger effort they are part of; and
- Make the Mission's relevance intuitively clear to the European citizens regardless of age, education, gender, ethnicity or background.

² Mission Ocean Twitter channel: <https://twitter.com/eumissionocean>

³ Prep4Blue's website: <https://prep4blue.eu>

2 Background information – Narrative Research

In this section we provide a horizon-scan of the different ways one can construct a Narrative and the important features to be taken into account. This research has inspired our work and the way we are constructing our narratives for the sake of this project.

2.1 Narrative: definition and importance

A narrative is a form of storytelling that can shape opinions and understandings of reality. It uses core elements (plot, characters, point of view, setting, theme, conflict, and style) to construct and/or alter people’s perspectives, relationships, attitudes, and even behaviors. Consequently, fiction and myths can become fact, and vice versa, in many minds.

Narratives are, therefore, incredibly powerful in their influential nature, often regardless of their truth. We’ve all seen the power a well-developed political narrative can have on public opinion and behavior, regardless of its honesty or accuracy.

2.2 Narrative: types, characteristics and structure

2.2.1 Narrative Types and Characteristics

There are mainly four types of narratives:

- **Descriptive** – focused on how the story’s setting, characters, and objects look and feel by using vivid imagery to introduce specific objects and ideas using personification and similes meant for total immersion in the world of the story (different from the limited perspective viewpoint narrative which strives to create immersion in a character’s inner world);
- **Linear** – told in chronological order with each scene followed by the next logical scene, e.g. quest or historical stories;
- **Nonlinear** - a nonlinear narrative in nonchronological order whereby the focus may be on character emotions and perspectives on the events in the story rather than the sequence in which they happen;
- **Viewpoint** - focused on the narrator’s perspective of the story’s events, usually character driven more than plot driven to explore facets of the protagonist’s personality and expose the audience to their thoughts (good for stories with perspective and personal growth themes).

Figure 1. Many Perspectives, One Narrative

Hereunder are three “non-linear narratives” examples of ocean narratives found in recent academic or government publications on the ocean:

- Example 1- The simplified narrative:

Figure 2 is of the presentation of science contributions to the *Mission Restore our Ocean and Waters by 2030* as found on the European Commission website (Source: ec.europa.eu/research-and-innovation/en/projects/exhibition/panoramas2022?s=03#3Ocean).

Figure 2. Science contributions to the Mission Ocean, illustrated on the European Commission website (Source: ec.europa.eu⁴)

⁴ EC representation of Mission Ocean:

<https://ec.europa.eu/research-and-innovation/en/projects/exhibition/panoramas2022?s=03#3Ocean>

- Example 2- The confused narrative:
Figure 3 is the horrendogram diagram published in a review of the confusing nature of law steering ocean conservation in England (Source: Boyes and Elliott, 2014⁵)

Figure 3. Horrendogram diagram on International, European and English legislation giving protection to the marine environment.

(Source: Boyes and Elliott, 2014 – DOI: [10.1016/j.marpolbul.2014.06.055](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.marpolbul.2014.06.055))

- Example 3 - The technology driven narrative:
The following (Figure 4) is an older picture of the contribution of the Global Ocean Observing System (GOOS) to understanding the ocean.

Figure 4. The (complex) Global Ocean Observing System (GOOS) as illustrated by Glynn Gorick
(Source: IOC GOOS - <http://unesdoc.unesco.org/images/0018/001878/187825E.pdf>)

⁵ Source: Boyes and Elliott, 2014 – DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.marpolbul.2014.06.055>

2.2.2 Narrative structure

Every narrative, even nonlinear narratives, is organized in some way. This is how the main character pursues their goal or faces the challenge presented to them. No matter how you structure your narrative, it has three distinct parts:

- **The beginning:**
This is where the reader meets your writing. Hooking their attention at the beginning is crucial.
- **The middle:**
The middle of your story or essay is where the action happens. This is where your protagonist faces one or more conflicts and reaches the climax, the point where the narrative pivots to the falling action after the protagonist either meets or fails to meet their goal.
- **The end:**
After the narrative’s climax, the ending wraps up loose story threads, satisfies readers’ remaining curiosities, and positions the protagonist for life after the story’s events.

Most scientific organizations now produce information for scientists on how their narrative can be told. Below is an example (Figure 5) produced by the American Geophysical Union.

Figure 5. Components of a basic story arc by the American Geophysical Union (AGU)
(Source: AGU Sharing Science - <https://connect.agu.org/sharingscience/virtual-learning-modules/storytelling/story-arc>)

2.3 Ocean and Mission Ocean's narrative context

Concerning the ocean, the dominant narrative focusing on sustainable human ocean interactions is based on the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) of the United Nations. At the EU-level, the focus has been on the EU Green Deal and its goals. From this has been distilled the three goals for the Mission Restore our Ocean and Waters by 2030:

1. Protect and restore marine and freshwater ecosystems and biodiversity, in line with the EU Biodiversity Strategy 2030;
2. Prevent and eliminate pollution of our ocean, seas and waters, in line with the EU Action Plan Towards Zero Pollution for Air, Water and Soil;
3. Make the sustainable blue economy carbon-neutral and circular, in line with the proposed European Climate Law and the holistic vision enshrined in the Sustainable Blue Economy Strategy.

Imagine what we could accomplish if everyone who hears our message were to join Mission Ocean and commit to it achieving its goals. For this reason, we want to tell inspirational stories and to be the visionary leaders who inspire everyone on behalf of Mission Ocean.

The narrative work in Prep4Blue is embedded in the above context and inspired by the work of the current generation of marine scientists, many of whom see their work as contributing to implementing the Sustainable Development Goals. As one recent study observes:

“To achieve [the sustainable development] goals, we need to change the narrative about the ocean to encourage us (governments, business, society, media, and scientists) to change our minds and behaviors. We need to move from only raising problems by documenting or predicting calamities to outlining pathways for scalable solutions (Borja et al. – DOI: [10.3389/fmars.2022.886027](https://doi.org/10.3389/fmars.2022.886027)⁶)”.

To that end, Lubchenco and Gaines (2019) propose a new ocean narrative:

“The ocean is not too big to fail, nor is it too big to fix, but it is too big and important to ignore”. (Lubchenco and Gaines, 2019 – DOI: [10.1126/SCIENCE.AAY2241](https://doi.org/10.1126/SCIENCE.AAY2241)⁷)

The narrative proposed in the above text has been similarly expressed in a variety of articles by marine scientists, including the following:

- Knowlton, N. “Doom and gloom won't save the world” Nature 544, 271 (2017). <https://doi.org/10.1038/544271a>

Similar approaches involving society overcoming challenges to achieve positive outcomes were taken by various international reports, including:

- Global Ocean Commission, From Decline to Recovery: A Rescue Package for the Global Ocean Report Summary, 2016
- WWF-US Oceans Strategy, September 2022.
- EuroNews Green News positive stories, <https://www.euronews.com/green/2022/11/14/here-are-all-the-positive-environmental-stories-from-2022-so-far>

⁷ <https://www.frontiersin.org/articles/10.3389/fmars.2022.886027/full>

- BBC Story Works Age of Change, Aspirational stories of humans in harmony with nature, <https://www.bbc.com/storyworks/specials/age-of-change/>

3 Prep4Blue's Mission Narrative

Mission Ocean is so large and vast that implying there is only one story to tell, one overarching message, would underserve its many ambitions. There are a number of narratives that can be used as part of Mission Ocean. However, as no resource is as precious or valuable to life on earth as water, we need everyone to understand that concept. Therefore, the overarching focus should always be on *“fostering awe around the ocean and our waters - inspiring respect and commitment to its health not only through the charter and its goals, but through every-day actions by everybody.”* We are focused on advocating for pristine, protected, and prosperous ocean and waters, and our messaging should always strive to promote an aim toward those values and goals.

Our role, as official partners of the Mission, is to inspire European communities, organizations, stakeholders, businesses, citizens, etc. toward achieving essential common goals by involving them directly in their design, implementation, and assessment. Our EC-funded Mission Ocean partner community, including Prep4Blue as well as the Lighthouses and other entities, can, and should, include everyone as our ocean and waters serve everyone.

Prep4Blue is committed to develop pilot visionary virtual and physical Mission communication spaces for future Mission efforts. The aim is to build a Mission “community” which connects and encompasses the many existing projects and initiatives at EU, national, and local levels, as well as inspire awe and wonder around the ocean - connecting people with things they deeply value and welcome - and eliciting interest in taking action.

Our role will be to help promote those narratives via our communications tools (see section 3.4). Whether utilizing the website to feature stories, TikTok to promote videos, or events to reach the masses, we can utilize a number of narratives to engage our various audiences.

For our purposes, we are committed to sharing a truthful narrative that inspires our audience to engage in and commit to the Mission, in any way they may be able (signing the charter, organizing local activities, making different life decisions, etc.). Our communications activities should always adhere to the overarching narratives relevant to Mission Ocean.

Figure 6 is a summary of the key aspects of the Mission narrative to be implemented by Prep4Blue.

Figure 6. Narrative Development from Mission Implementation Plan to Mission Community

3.1 What and who are the Protagonists

The Mission Restore our Ocean and Waters by 2030 has taken up the EU goals highlighting a sense of collective action. The challenges are too big, too complex or otherwise unwieldy thus requiring “us” as actors to implement “Our Goals”. Finally, personal responsibility and action are required to change what is often referred to as “minds and behaviours” in order to transform The Goals and Our Goals into “My Goals”.

On a conceptual level, the protagonists here are individuals and groups that:

- Can be clearly defined.
- Struggle to solve a problem or achieve a goal in line with the Mission.
- May face a struggle to implement that goal, perhaps due to external circumstances.
- Have agency which moves the story forward.
- Are hopefully ultimately successful in achieving their goal.

3.2 Narrative levels

Prep4Blue will focus on three levels of activity, which are key to implementing the EU Mission Restore our Ocean and Waters by 2030: My Mission, Our Mission and EU Mission (see Figure 7 below).

This in order to reinforce the sense that individuals are part of a community that is striving to achieve certain aims, in this case the EU Mission Ocean goals.

Figure 7. Building a Mission Community between the individual and EU levels

3.3 Narrative characteristics

Prep4Blue will showcase work being carried out by individuals or groups that have committed to the Mission goals, e.g. by signing the [Mission Charter](#)⁸ or having received funding. In line with the Mission Ocean Implementation Plan, four elements will comprise how work is showcased by Prep4Blue:

1. Authentic and realistic, reflecting appropriately the efforts being made to overcome whatever challenges exist to achieving the three Mission goals. This means that some narrative elements will not correspond entirely with the intended narrative of the European Commission or the European Union.
2. Content-focused, emphasizing “scalable and replicable, excellent and impact-driven research and innovation solutions (technological, business, social and governance) and demonstration activities”.
3. Community-oriented, reflecting the “basin-wide cooperation, commitment and deployment of solutions” in each of the Lighthouse areas.
4. Inclusive and diverse, incorporating tried and tested deliberative democracy mechanisms and social innovation practices, participatory governance approaches, mobilising and empowering citizens for the co-design and co-implementation of solutions.

Considering the prompts above and their potential influence, **we encourage our Mission partners** to utilize the narrative themes in ways that will help:

- Foster knowledge, acceptance, and support of the Mission;
- Inspire and boost Mission engagement across all audiences;
- Encourage signing the Mission Charter (for legal entities only);
- Create a new way of working together (everyone is invited; this is a collaboration, not a competition);
- Spotlight Mission activities/work for increased confidence and positive perceptions surrounding Mission Ocean;

⁸ Mission Implementation Charter – Call for action : <https://ec.europa.eu/eusurvey/files/e31343c3-92af-42fb-8a19-146d61201fea/b16cc951-2f1e-4046-adf8-43fe836df7d0>

- Encourage attendance at Mission events (citizen assemblies, workshops, trainings, etc.) for increased public participation/citizen engagement;
- Spread the word about funding to engage businesses and organizations, fostering innovation, engagement, and economic stimulus;
- Collect data to promote appropriate marine science integration and shared knowledge;
- Spotlight various interesting Mission Ocean subjects (new technology, projects, people doing good works, marine creatures, etc.) to foster knowledge and awareness amongst the public and other stakeholders;
- Create awareness and activism around an issue (plastic pollution, deep sea mining, sustainable fishing, daily personal choices, etc.) to drive personal accountability, investment, and dedication to the cause.

3.4 Possible Narratives for Use

Here below (Table 1 **Error! Reference source not found.**) we have various narrative prompts and how this would influence the protagonists on the Mission awareness, perception, and relationships.

Table 1. Possible Narratives for use in and for the Mission Ocean

Narrative Prompt/Storytelling	Potential Influence on Mission Awareness, Perception, & Relationships
<p>Who has signed the Charter and why (profiles, sectors, testimonies). What are they doing to meet their commitments? Which companies are funded under Mission Ocean and doing the “boots on the ground” work? What exactly are they doing? Ocean SuperStars: who’s who and who’s doing what for the health of our ocean and waters?</p>	<p>Demonstrate community, business, and organizational support and commit to the Mission. Profiling businesses making an actual impact may inspire local communities to engage. It could also enhance business opportunities and successes. Upsell the idea of becoming an ocean celebrity, inspiring pride in being part of Mission Ocean and engaging all audiences on a wider level to contribute and share.</p>
<p>What are the “Lighthouses” and what are they doing? How will they help meet the three goals?</p>	<p>Spotlight successful funding campaigns making a real difference on the ground – demonstrating the Mission’s viability and importance in our future.</p>
<p>What are European Blue Parks and how do they benefit me/us/society/the world? Is there one I can visit?</p>	<p>Engage the public in visiting and appreciating our ocean and water environments, inspiring awe and wonder, encouraging tourism and activism, and facilitating genuine caring.</p>
<p>What defines “good ocean/water/ecosystem health” and which areas are healthy vs. unhealthy? What’s involved in restoring marine and freshwater ecosystems and how can I contribute/support these initiatives? Learn about series (fisheries, algae production, sea creatures, bio-based solutions, etc.) Which movies can I watch to learn more about the ocean and waters? What can I do in my daily life to help as “just one person”?</p>	<p>Expand public knowledge, increase awareness, and build confidence to contribute to public actions toward more healthy ecosystems.</p>
<p>What actions are being taken at the national, regional, or organization level to prevent/minimize/remediate marine/freshwater pollution?</p>	<p>Build confidence in the EU/EC efforts, including funding programs under Mission Ocean to foster public buy-in and appreciate the spending/funding commitment.</p>

Narrative Prompt/Storytelling	Potential Influence on Mission Awareness, Perception, & Relationships
<p>What is a “blue economy”? Who does it affect financially, and how does it work? Investors’ shift towards nature-based solutions – green/blue investing Which areas are being affected by sea level rise and what are the socio-economic impacts?</p>	<p>Foster knowledge and understanding about the real world implications of how our ocean and waters are used and the financial impacts to every segment of society, thereby increasing awareness and public caring.</p>
<p>What are the latest advances in “blue tech” and “big blue data” (biodiversity/pollution monitoring, European Digital Twin Ocean, tools and gadgets, etc.)</p>	<p>Demonstrate interesting and captivating tech and information to drive public and stakeholder excitement around ocean industry.</p>
<p>What are the other Missions and how do they interact with Mission Ocean?</p>	<p>Expand awareness of the Missions – potentially reaching a much more diverse audience who may find a link to Mission Ocean through other Missions, and vice versa.</p>

3.5 Implementation tools of Prep4Blue for the narrative

Prep4Blue’s work packages are collectively creating tools and methodologies to help Mission partners with their work, in sharing their stories, and in achieving the goals of the Mission. WP2 will draw on the work of Prep4Blue partners and from input from all Mission projects and contributions shape the various narratives and promoting protected, pristine, prosperous from the three categories of My Mission, Our Mission, the EU Mission (see section 3.2).

The narratives from across the Mission will be showcased via three pilot products outlined in Task 2.3 (T2.3) *“Narrative & Strategy Testing Through Pilot Campaigns & Spaces”*. T2.3 will pilot the narrative and Communications Strategy (see future deliverable D2.2) through a social media campaign, virtual spaces, and intergenerational and inclusive physical spaces as venues for meetings, interactions, exhibitions, etc., to engage Mission contributors and citizens across Europe. The task will organize at least two exhibitions/public events in iconic spaces (e.g., Ocean Space | Venice) with artists, designers, architects, the European Bauhaus, and other initiatives to showcase the Mission and its contributors. These products will be positioned as globally-visible contributions to the UN Ocean Decade.

Subtask 2.3.1: *“Pilot a social media campaign, including public competitions, aimed at bringing Mission information to young people”*. This task will draw on and coordinate with other campaigns across Europe to engage citizens.

Subtask 2.3.2: *“Conceptualize, design, and pilot an interactive, multidimensional virtual Mission space (website)”*, including an overview of all Mission contributions and Mission-related events. This task will include working with online venue developers to explore the most advanced, open-source, accessible (CMS) software available and develop a virtual space pilot. This task will showcase progress in Mission implementation (e.g., a Progress Dashboard and Map). It is intended be used by both the public and Mission community with public and private.

Subtask 2.3.3: *“Conceptualize, design, and pilot with potential venues from around the world physical Mission spaces”* that serve to exhibit Mission contributions and as venues to hold Mission-related activities (e.g., citizen assemblies, foresight workshops, future labs, etc.) in Europe.

3.5.1 Website

Within Prep4Blue, a website to promote the Mission is currently under development: missionoceanwaters.eu⁹

The core menu (see Table 2) will reflect the three-tiered approach and highlight interactive content.

Table 2. Core menu items of the Mission’s website

Core Menu Item	Content
Home	“Home” will consist of 4 separate Lighthouse pages
About	Focus on the “EU Mission”. A descriptive page with links to official pages, a calendar, background information and more.
Explore	Focus on “Our Mission” with an overview of all contributions to the Mission, esp. EU funded projects as well as national and local contributions (e.g., Charter signatories)
Contribute	A service to the Mission community with social media trainings esp. for Charter signatories, Mission projects, etc.
Mission Ocean Academy	Focus on “My Mission” with an overview of citizen science activities (e.g., Plastic Pirates) and testimonials.

Each of the Lighthouses will be represented by a “scene” (see Figure 8 below) intended to showcase the Lighthouse and contributing individuals and activities. These scenes will employ descriptive and viewpoint narratives with the aim to “emotionalize” the Mission through interactive elements which involve and are meant to be fun. The user is immersed, in which they interact with people, their surroundings, products and objects, in which they experience first-hand brands and events.

Figure 8. Scenes/Illustrations for each lighthouse on the Prep4Blue website.
Lighthouses from left to right: Atlantic-Arctic (picture of Cork), Baltic-North Sea (picture of Hamburg), Mediterranean (picture of Palermo) and Danube (picture of Dunărea)

3.5.2 Social Media Pilot Activities

The narrative will also be reflected in the social media work of Prep4Blue. At least two activities will be carried out in this regard:

- Mission Ocean Academy will offer services to contributors to the mission in order to support the visibility from their Mission (*My Mission*) to the Mission overall (*Our Mission* and *EU Mission*).

⁹ Mission’s website : missionoceanwaters.eu

- A cohort of Mobile Journalists (MOJOs), consisting mainly of students, will be funded to showcase contributions to the Mission through video diaries and similar. This will link individual Missions with the larger community Mission.

3.5.3 Exhibition and/or event

The aim is conceptualize, design, and pilot with potential venues (e.g., museums and aquaria) from around the world physical Mission spaces that serve to exhibit Mission contributions and as venues to hold Mission-related activities (e.g., citizen assemblies, foresight workshops, future labs, etc.) in Europe.

A decision has not yet been taken about exactly how this task will be implemented. Close cooperation with the Mission Secretariat and other relevant actors will be essential.

3.5.4 Workshops

The approach (see section 3.4) was tested in two different ways in recent workshops. The first workshop was held with Prep4Blue partners, all of whom are informed about the Mission and its goals. The aim in this first workshop was to get creative feedback on how they perceive the Mission. The guidance offered is attached in Annex 1.

The second workshop was with approximately 30 coastal scientists attending the 3rd Coast in Transition Conference in Hamburg from 9-11 November 2022. The participants in this narrative workshop were generally very interested in the Mission Restore our Ocean and Waters by 2030, but none had any direct contact or information about the Mission. However, they had been introduced to the concept of Mission-oriented research as many were project partners in one of the three “ocean Missions” being funded in Germany by the Federal Ministry of Education and Research (BMBF).

A survey was given to participants of this session, who were mostly coastal scientists with some NGO representatives. Not surprisingly most were interested in the Green Deal goal protection and restoration, but surprising was that even the scientific community feels itself to be a full partner in all aspects of the Ocean and Waters Mission from basic science to co-implementing measures in the sea. For more details on the presentation and questionnaire see Annex 2.

4 Conclusion

Building the narrative for the Mission Ocean, seeing the many interested actors and protagonists, will need several iterations. Also, it’s important to note that the Narrative will need to be adapted to the concerned audience. We believe that using the three-layer narrative model and construct our layers in a non-linear way, results on the biggest impact to our targeted audience.

5 ANNEXES

Annex 1 - Prep4Blue WP2 Workshop Report (14.9.2022)

WP2 Session Minutes: Prep4Blue Kick-off Meeting Brussels, 14 September 2022

Overview: During the Prep4Blue Kick-off Meeting on September 14 in Brussels, Belgium, Stefan Fritz and Wendy Namisnik from WP2 (Creating a Visionary Narrative, Communications & Spaces) co-led a PowerPoint presentation (see Annex III) on WP2's work for the project. This included a discussion of: tasks and deliverables (narrative guide, communication plan, social media campaign, website, events/exhibitions), goals and expected outcomes, timeline, linkages with other WPs and projects/initiatives, and short-term next steps. Stefan also provided a demonstration of the website (in draft stage), including a video featuring 360-degree technology that will be utilized in various areas of the site. Additionally, after the presentation, they led a working session with an abstract focus on Mission identity and narrative (see page 2 for WP2 Working Session Overview).

Key takeaways from audience engagement after the PowerPoint presentation:

- We should go really big with our “visionary narrative” – “rewilding” is an example.
- Our introductory website video was uninspiring considering we are trying to be visionary.
- We should change the imagery associated with negative connotations on the website, e.g., the fish in the nets.
- It's important to distinguish that it isn't necessarily the EC that has initiated this kind of restore our ocean and waters work; it is the scientist and researchers, the boots on the ground that have been doing this for years and are finally getting some funding.
- We should not feel a heavy burden to carry the Mission and the EC cannot comment on how forthcoming initiatives (e.g., tender) will affect our (overlapping) work, so we should continue on as it could be a year before anything happens.
- We, as Prep4Blue, should be recognizable as part of the Mission and partners should follow us on Twitter as some of our social media efforts have already started.

Clarifications: Important to note and that may have been misunderstood by the audience is that the website is in a draft stage and images were selected by the web developers without our input. They are all subject to change, and, ideally, images that demonstrate successes/failures should come from our partners, lighthouses, and other initiatives. The styling of the site with three themes demonstrating success vs. failure were well received and will be further developed so as not to offend Mission Ocean stakeholders (where possible).

Next Steps: In the short-term, our focus is on developing the narrative guide and launching the website. At the November Cork event we will likely hold another narrative workshop and re-shoot the website video to include more stakeholders and capture more dramatic footage/messaging. We're also in the process of contracting with a social media expert for the campaign and have created the Communications Cooperative (first meeting in Oct).

WP2 Working Session Overview

Following WP2's presentation on their Mission Ocean work, and as part of the WP2 working session, attendees were split into five groups based on the colors assigned to them for the event (purple, blue, green, orange, red). Each group was presented with the same 15 questions (see Annex I below) regarding assigning an identity to "Mission Ocean," specifically if it were a living being. The groups were given about 40 minutes to answer the questions, create a sketch of their vision of Mission Ocean based on their answers, and then later present their findings to all participants (see posters in Annex II).

The exercise was meant to get Prep4Blue partners to step away from the administrative concept of the Mission as simply "another European Commission project," and rather think creatively about it as force for change, an identity unto itself, a being that can present a story to the world on behalf of our ocean and waters to inspire change, commitment, and action for a better world. Overall, the activity (answers, drawings, presentations) will help inform WP2's work on the narrative and other communication deliverables as well as hopefully inspire all Prep4Blue partners to utilize creative approaches when communicating Mission Ocean.

Annex I: Working Session - Mission Ocean Identity Questions & Group Answers

1. Is it a gender? If so, which gender?
 - Gender neutral, gender free, non-binary, flexible
2. What kind of voice(s) do you hear when it speaks?
 - Inspiring, many voices/accents/languages, wise, peculiar, singing, dolphins, water running, whales
 - Cousteau, Attenborough, Adele
3. What does it look like?
 - Soft, circular, flowing, multi-organism, endless, chimeric creature – adapts to many goals and audiences, chameleon, sea/water/waves
 - Catamaran, lighthouse
4. What does it taste and smell like?
 - Fresh, damp, moist, healthy, oxygen, salty
5. What sounds does it make?
 - Melodical, whispering, musical, fresh, healthy
6. How does it feel to your touch?
 - Strength, liquid, fluid, soft, wet

7. What images do you see along with it?
 - Positivity, fish, deep sea, wind, mountains, sand and pebbles, changing color, both scary and inspiring
8. How does it make you feel emotionally?
 - Motivated
9. How does it make you feel physically? Which of your senses awaken and how?
 - Energized, exposed, scared, frustrated, would like to speak
10. What color(s) is it?
 - Teal, blue, reflective, shimmering, shiny, blue/multicolour, purple, green
11. What is it feeling?
 - Responsibility, adventurous, full of life, exploring, connection, harmony, friendship, peace, protective, safe
12. What does it want?
 - Action, participation, engagement
13. What message(s) is it sending you/the world?
 - Call to action, plea, emergency, hope, connect people
14. What makes it thrive versus suffer?
 - Collaboration, hugs, rivers, diversity, energy, food
15. Where does it come from & where does it go?
 - Come from common concern goes to people, from source to the ocean, from head to hands
 - Eternal circle, ancient

Annex II: Working Session - Group Presentation Posters

ORANGE

1. GENDER NEUTRAL
2. INSPIRING
3. SOFT, CIRCULAR
FLOWING
4. FRESH
5. MELODICAL
6. POWER/STRENGTH
7. POSITIVITY
8. MOTIVATED
9. ENERGIZED
10. TEAL
11. RESPONSIBILITY
12. ACTION, PARTICIPATION, ENGAGEMENT
13. URGENCY, PLEA, CALL TO ACTION
14. COLLABORATION
15. COMES FROM
COMMON CONCERN
GOES TO PEOPLE

GREEN

1. Non binary : male/female
2. Many voices / accents / languages / wise voice / peculiar voice
3. Multi organism creature / endless thing
4. Damp, moist taste
5. Whispering / musical sound
6. Liquid / fluid / soft / jelly / intangible
- 7
- 8
- 9
10. Blue / silver / shimmer / shiny
11. Adventurous / exploring / full of life
12. Connection / Harmony / Friendship / Peace
13. Justice / motivation / Hope / Connect people
14. Fair
15. From source to the ocean / From head to hands

RED

Community

What makes it things?
HUGS

Octopus Moustache
only the arms are ever
seen cleaning things up

The creature wants
to swim in
clean waters.

IMPRESSED
WOW
WOW

BLUE (MUTE)
&
multicolor?

disorientation
(changes
grade and
color?)

Feeling:
SAFE
protection

Chimeric creature
to adapt to
many goals
and audiences.

WAVE
SOUND

≠ ATTITUDE
≠ FACET

Feeling:
Wet, softish

Cameleon changing
colors.

Feeling:
Calming
Relaxation

VOICE

→ Cousin

→ D. Attenborough

→ D. Adle

~~PURPLE~~

BLUE

*Gender-Free.
→ many languages
have gender for the
sea

WAVE

NOISES
→ singing, sirens.
→ dolphins
→ water running
→ whales. → laughing

TASTE
→ fresh air, oxygen.
salty,
→

SMELL
→ fresh.
→ healthy.

LOOKS
→ dynamic
→ sea, water, wave.
→ wave from all perspective
→

MISSION
→ teenager, a bit
lost. with activism
enthusiasm, energy.

FEELINGS it's
→ exposed. → scared
→ would like to speak
→ would like to act.
→ frustrated. like baby
because it can't speak

TOUCH
→ fluid.
→ warm
→

IMAGES:
→ fish, deep sea
→ wind
→ mountains.
→ sand + pebbles

Thrive?
→ energy. → bad.
→ rivers. → humans
→ diversity.

MISSION word.
Don't like it.
Bad connotation.
not bottom-up
→ not religious things

(What does it
wake you feel?)
→ peace or scared
(protecting or protected)
→ female feelings
→ hopeful.

IMAGES)
→ changing colour
→ both scary + inspiring
→

COMES FROM GOES TO:
→ eternal.
→ circle.
→ ancient

SUFFER
→ Ego
→ humans.
→ indifference / ignorance
→

We can
do it! Now!
Go blue and
green!

It's our
mission. We
will do it

CO²

Pentahelix actors

PREP4BLUE

METHODS AND TOOLS FOR MISSION OCEAN & WATERS

WP2 Overview

Creating a Visionary Narrative, Communication & Spaces

Stefan Fritz, Wendy Namisnik

Prep4Blue Kick-off Meeting

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prep4blue.eu | missionoceanwaters.eu

#MissionOcean #EUmissions #HorizonEU

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2. Goals & Expected Outcomes
3. Timeline
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6. Virtual Space (Website) – Pilot
7. Website Demo
8. Physical Spaces (Events/Exhibitions) - Pilot
9. Linkages - Communication Cooperative
10. Short-term Next Steps
11. Narrative Brainstorming Session

Tasks & Deliverables

Tasks	Task 2.1. Narrative Guide	Task 2.2. Communication Plan	Task 2.3.1 Social Media Campaign (Pilot)	Task 2.3.2 Virtual Space (Website) (Pilot)	Task 2.3.3 Physical Spaces (Events/Exhibitions) (Pilot)
Deliverables	D2.1 Narrative Guide (M6)	D2.2 Communication Plan (M9)	D2.3 Interim Implementation Report On Tasks & Proposed Deliverables (M12)		D2.4 Final SWOT Analysis Of WP Product Implementation (M36)
Products & Services	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Workshops • Narrative Guide 	Communication Plan	Social Media Campaign	Virtual Space (Website)	Two Exhibitions/Public Events In Iconic Spaces (e.g., Ocean Space Venice) With Artists, Designers, Architects, & Other Initiatives To Showcase The Mission & Its Contributors

Goals & Expected Outcomes

Goals

- Create inspiring & accessible platforms for communicating the Mission.
- Increase stakeholder & citizen awareness about, & engagement with, the Mission.
- Promote the Lighthouses & their contributions (show the successes, highlight the impacts, encourage mobilization, & convey the principles/values of why we're doing this).
- Advocate for and assist with consistency in messaging/branding across Mission partners.
- Provide helpful tools, information, & support in Mission communication activities.

Expected Outcomes

- There is increased access to Mission information & therefore an actual increase in understanding of, and engagement with, the Mission.
- Prep4Blue partners, other CSAs, & Mission-related initiatives have & use the proper branding/messaging tools for instant recognizability and Mission cohesion.
- Stories that champion the Mission are published and circulated outside "echo chambers" for broader public appreciation, understanding, and engagement.
- Mission contributors & partners understand the larger effort they are part of & can more efficiently collaborate as well as articulate their work across audiences.

No one is left behind in the achievement of the Mission.

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Timeline

Narrative Guide & Communication Plan

- **Narrative Guide** – Identified ways to motivate, educate, & entertain through Mission stories
 - This guide should help partners tell captivating stories through a distinguished Mission communication style (tone, voice, & feel) to inspire & engage the public in the Mission.
- **Communication Plan** – A collection of tools (branding, imagery, rules, templates), information (links, channels, established guidelines), & recommendations (best practices) to convey messages to audiences across platforms while remaining true to the Mission brand.
 - The EC has already published a comprehensive communication strategy and source files, & our plan will pull heavily from those to advocate consistency among partners.

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Social Media Campaign - Pilot

Demonstrate a creative & successful campaign around a Mission subject(s) to drive engagement across audiences.

- Lighthouses, Blue Parks, & 3 Green Deal goals will be explored through themes.
- Early themes include: plastics waste, leisure/sports, nature restoration (including habitat and animal protection), & food.
- We'll engage with ECOPs & social media professional(s) to implement this task.

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Virtual Space (Website)- Pilot

Provide an attractive, informative, & easy-to-navigate website to learn about & engage with the Mission

- Cutting-edge, 360-degree videos featuring dynamic ocean/water actors in Mission landscapes (some linked to social media & events)
- Varied & dynamic content (stories, Lighthouse details/successes, event calendar, data, cinema, helpful links, etc.)
- Easy-to-use content management system; various partners may be able contribute directly
- Available in multiple languages (dubbing/language selection/auto-translate)
- May serve as main hub (one-stop-shop) through which all Mission-related initiatives are hosted or directly linked/accessible
- Could be absorbed by future Mission Implement Platform so information isn't lost (no need to "reinvent the wheel")

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Website Demo

PROSPERITY

Physical Spaces (Events/Exhibitions) - Pilot

“Market spaces” could showcase Mission contributions & successes, facilitate exchanging ideas, encourage public participation, & promote market creation. The first event will likely happen in Venice.

Ocean Space | Venice

Varvakeios Agora Market | Athens

Linkages

Establish the WP2 Communications Cooperative

- Goals & Objectives
 - Share information & solicit content/stories for development & promotion
 - Keep communication channels open among stakeholders so silos don't form
 - Provide tools, resources, recommendations, & support for communications activities
- Members
 - 1 representative from each Prep4blue WP
 - Alberto from CINEA & Natalia from Prep4Blue to be in CC
 - We will invite 1 contact from each Lighthouse & Blue Parks (CSAs)
 - Work collaboratively with the implementation platform & other relevant projects once established
- Structure
 - Mailing list
 - Shared folder to access tools/assets
 - Possible access to our website & social media channels to cross-promote (granted permissions, etc.)
 - Option for engaging local stories to be captured in campaigns (videos/photos, articles, social media, etc.)
 - Meetings &/or workshops may be held to serve a variety of wants/needs

Short-term Next Steps

- Communication Cooperative 1st Meeting (October 2022)
 - Access to tools/assets
 - General update on communication needs/wants/next steps
- Publish (within 3-6 months from today)
 - Narrative Guide
 - Communication Plan
 - Website
- Grow Our Social Media Presence & Capabilities
 - Continue to post regularly and acquire new stories & information (<https://twitter.com/eumissionocean>)
 - Hire social media intern to more actively manage channels/campaign
 - Contract with social media expert/advisor for campaign strategy & implementation

Ensure Recognizability & Maximize Impact

Narrative Brainstorming

Tell us about your vision of the Mission if the Mission was a living being.

1. Is it a gender? If so, which gender?
2. What kind of voice(s) do you hear when it speaks?
3. What does it look like?
4. What does it taste & smell like?
5. What sounds does it make?
6. How does it feel to your touch?
7. What images do you see along with it?
8. How does it make you feel emotionally?
9. How does it make you feel physically? Which of your senses awaken & how?
10. What color(s) is it?
11. What is it feeling?
12. What does it want?
13. What message(s) is it sending you/the world?
14. What makes it thrive versus suffer?
15. Where does it come from & where does it go?

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Annex 2 - Workshop Future Coast (10.11.2022)

Coast in Transition 2022

Mission-oriented research

Konsortium Deutsche Meeresforschung
German Marine Research Consortium

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What is the role of science in restoring our ocean and waters by 2030?

How much responsibility does science have, if it has access to the best available knowledge?

Motivation for this Session

The symposium „Küste im Wandel“ seeks to discuss:

... the increased need for **results and options for action from marine research** for sustainable coastal management.

... den erhöhten Bedarf nach Ergebnissen und Handlungsoptionen aus der Meeresforschung für ein nachhaltiges Küstenmanagement zu diskutieren.

KDM, as a representative of the interests of German marine research, needs:

research results, success stories, ideas for the future, etc. for its consultations with parliamentarians, government officials, industry associations, NGOs, as well as other societal groups.

KDM is a partner in the Prep4Blue EU project tasked with developing the narrative of the EU's Mission Restore our Ocean and Waters by 2030.

EUROPEAN UNION

EU MISSIONS

RESTORE OUR OCEAN & WATERS

Concrete solutions for our greatest challenges

#EUmissions #HorizonEU #MissionOcean

What Makes the iPhone so Smart?

Figure 13 from *The Entrepreneurial State: debunking public vs. private sector myths* (2015, p. 116)

Context for Mission-oriented Science funding and policy

Die größten Sorgen der Deutschen

welt

Quelle: EY Germany

EU Priorities in 2022

- implementing the European Green Deal,
- achieving a Europe fit for the digital age,
- delivering an economy that works for people,
- making Europe stronger in the world,
- promoting our European way of life, incl. when facing health crises,
- protecting and strengthening our democracy and defending common European values.

5 Missions to address societal challenges

Adaptation to Climate Change

Cancer

Climate-neutral and Smart Cities

Soil Deal for Europe

Restore our Ocean and Waters by 2030

How often does a Sustainable Development Goal appear in leaders' top six priorities?

We asked leaders the following question: "Based upon your experience, what are the most important issues for advancing [your country's] development?" Respondents identified up to six goals from a fixed list of 16 SDGs that they believed to be most important for advancing their country's development.

Horizon Europe – the key funding tool

- Implementation via a portfolio of actions, e.g. research projects, policy measures or even legislative initiatives to achieve goals that could not be achieved through individual actions.
- Funding: 500 Million to 2025
- Evaluation in 2023

The Ocean Mission – Goals, Structure & Resources

The Ocean Mission – Goals in Detail

PROTECT AND RESTORE MARINE AND FRESHWATERS ECOSYSTEMS AND BIODIVERSITY

- Protect at least 30% and strictly protect 10% EU's sea areas
- Restore 25.000 km free flowing rivers
- Marine nature restoration targets (incl. degraded seabeds, coastal ecosystems)

PREVENT AND ELIMINATE POLLUTION OF OUR OCEANS, SEAS AND WATERS

- Reduce by at least 50% plastic litter
- Reduce by at least 30% microplastics
- Reduce by at least 50% nutrient losses, chemical pesticides

MAKE THE BLUE ECONOMY CARBON-NEUTRAL AND CIRCULAR

- Net zero maritime emissions
- Zero carbon aquaculture,
- Low carbon multipurpose use of marine space

NOTE: Funding is intended to support projects delivering these goals.

The Ocean Mission – Lighthouses

Lighthouses to pilot, demonstrate, develop and deploy Mission activities across EU seas and river basins

Baltic & North sea basin

MAKE THE BLUE ECONOMY
CARBON- NEUTRAL AND
CIRCULAR

Mediterranean sea basin

PREVENT AND ELIMINATE
POLLUTION OF OUR OCEAN,
SEAS AND WATERS

Danube river basin

PROTECT AND RESTORE MARINE
AND FRESHWATERS
ECOSYSTEMS AND BIODIVERSITY

Atlantic & Arctic coast

Cancer Mission

By 2030, more than 3 million lives saved, living longer and better

Ensure Equitable Access

Prevent
What is
Preventable

Optimise,
Diagnosis &
Treatment

Support
Quality
of Life

Areas
of Action

Understand

Focus of KDM
Actions to
date:
Ensuring that
science is a
core part of the
mission

Support for
Project
Proposals

Calls approx.
120 Euros
Million/Year

More
Events

Activities
implemented with
COM, BMBF/PT, DE-
Partner, EP, INT-
Partner

Influencing
the Narrative

EU Decision

EC Proposal

G7 Coop
Ocean
Plastics Lab

Events

Exchanges
with Policy
Makers

The Contribution of KDM to Mission development

Task:

Creating a Visionary Narrative,
Communications & Spaces

Develop a strong Mission Narrative

Goal:

To showcase the value of
investing in ocean and coastal
science and innovation with a
view to shaping the future of
ocean policy and marine
research policy.

Prepare an overarching Mission
Communication Strategy

Designing and piloting innovative
physical and virtual Mission Spaces for
the Mission community and general
population, pilot website, pilot
exhibition, pilot social media campaign

What is the science narrative?

The contribution of science and innovation – the simplified version

<https://ec.europa.eu/research-and-innovation/en/projects/exhibition/panoramas2022?s=03#3Ocean>

The contribution of science and innovation

The horrendogram "confused" reality

(1) In 2013 the WFD replaced the Dangerous Sub. Dir.; Freshwater Fish Dir.; Shellfish Waters Dir. & Groundwater Dir.

(2) The network of MPAs in England will consist of EMS/Natura 2000 (SACs & SPAs), SSSIs, Ramsar sites and MCZs

(3) The UK is not a signatory to this Convention however a number of public statements have been produced that confirm its endorsement of the rules in its Annex

All regulated activities in the English marine environment consider UK marine policy drivers such as the UK High Level Marine Objectives 2009, the UK Marine Policy Statement (4) and various National Policy Statements

The ease of understanding EU Commission press releases

The contribution of science and innovation – the DFG version

A "realistic" narrative, e.g. saving Venice

Sediment Transport

Seagrass/Salt marsh restoration

Seagrass modelling

Functional biodiversity modelling

Moses Barrier

What is our narrative (account of connected events)?

Our story?

... concerning the contribution of science to restoring our ocean and waters by 2030?

What KDM activities will we support with this narrative exercise?

Mission Pilot Social Media Campaign

Mission Pilot Website

Mission Pilot Exhibition

REST-COAST EU Project
Science Policy Briefings and Briefing Papers

KDM Strategy Group Multi-Use and MPAs

A narrative exercise

A narrative exercise

A multinational offshore wind farm operator is seeking to develop a coastal area for a new wind farm.

As a compensation measure, an equally large area adjacent to the wind farm is to be renaturalized.

The plan is to guide/support the design and implementation of both the wind farm and the renaturation area through scientific projects.

What could a scientific contribution to restoration look like?

Sample of Ocean-related topics in WP 2023-24 in Horizon Europe Cluster 6

HORIZON-CL6-2023-BIODIV-01-2: Impact of light and noise pollution on biodiversity

HORIZON-CL6-2023-BIODIV-01-5: Understanding and reducing bycatch of protected species

HORIZON-CL6-2023-BIODIV-01-6: Restoration of deep-sea habitats

HORIZON-CL6-2023-BIODIV-01-7: Demonstration of marine and coastal infrastructures as hybrid blue-grey Nature-based Solutions

HORIZON-CL6-2023-FARM2FORK-01-8: Using automatic species recognition and artificial intelligence to fight illegal fish discards and revolutionise fisheries control

HORIZON-CL6-2023-CircBio-01-11: Novel culturing of aquatic organisms for blue biotechnology applications

HORIZON-CL6-2024-CircBio-01-10: Targeting aquatic extremophiles for sourcing novel enzymes, drugs, metabolites and chemicals

HORIZON-CL6-2023-ZEROPOLLUTION-01-2: Integrated assessment and monitoring of emerging pollutants in the marine environment

HORIZON-CL6-2023-ZEROPOLLUTION-01-3: Tackling human and climate change induced pollution in the Arctic - building resilient socio-ecological systems

HORIZON-CL6-2023-ZEROPOLLUTION-01-2: Integrated assessment and monitoring of emerging pollutants in the marine environment

HORIZON-CL6-2023-ZEROPOLLUTION-01-3: Tackling human and climate change induced pollution in the Arctic - building resilient socio-ecological systems

HORIZON-CL6-2023-CLIMATE-01-3: Ocean and coastal waters carbon- and biodiversity-rich ecosystems and habitats in Europe and the Polar Regions

HORIZON-CL6-2023-CLIMATE-01-8: Closing the research gaps on Essential Ocean Variables (EOVs) in support of global assessments

HORIZON-CL6-2024-CLIMATE-01-6: Ocean models for seasonal to decadal regional climate impacts and feedbacks

HORIZON-CL6-2024-COMMUNITIES-01-3: Participation and empowerment of Arctic coastal, local, and indigenous communities in environmental decision-making

HORIZON-CL6-2023-GOVERNANCE-01-11: Reducing observation gaps in the land-sea interface area

HORIZON-CL6-2024-GOVERNANCE-01-4: Supporting the All-Atlantic Ocean Research and Innovation Alliance and Declaration

Contacts in the KDM Secretariat (as of November 2022)

(Dr.) Yekaterina Astafyeva
Mikrobiologie & Biotechnologie

Blue Carbon
Biotech

JPI Oceans
- Blue Carbon
- Ocean Carbon Capacities
- Licht und Lärm

BMBF Finanziert

Dr. Jan-Stefan Fritz
Politikwissenschaften und Geographie

KDM-Gremien
Strategiegruppen
Internationales, insb. EU, UN, OECD,

NKP UN World Ocean Assessment

EU Mission Gesundes Meer

Atlantik Kooperation

Dr. Jella Kandziora
Ökonomie und Ingenieur

NKP G7 FSOI
Ozeanbeobachtung
Beziehungen zu BMBF und BMUV

JPI Oceans
- Plastik
- Verschmutzung

BMBF Finanziert

Sebastian Konitzer
Umweltmanagement und Verwaltung

Finanzen
Verwaltung
Multimedia

Wendy Namisnik
Kommunikation

EU Mission "Restore our Ocean and Waters by 2030"

Atlantik Kooperation
Nachwuchsvernetzung

Dr. Alexandra-Sophie Roy
Marine Biologie

Koordination,
Zukunftsforum Ozean

Atlantikkooperation

Jonathan Heimer
Student,
Meeresumwelt, Uni Oldenburg

Ozeanbeobachtung
Küste und Blauer Ozean –Visualisierung der Arbeit der Strategiegruppen und der deutschen Beiträge

Alfred-Wegener-Institut Helmholtz-Zentrum für Polar- und Meeresforschung,
Bremerhaven

Bundesamt für Seeschifffahrt und Hydrographie, Hamburg

Bundesanstalt für Geowissenschaften & Rohstoffe, Hannover

Centrum für Erdsystemforschung & Nachhaltigkeit, Uni Hamburg

Dep't Maritime Systeme Interdisziplinäre Fakultät, Uni Rostock

Deutsches Meeresmuseum, Stralsund

Deutsches Schiffahrtsmuseum, Bremerhaven

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Survey - Your coastal research priorities "Options for Action"

The KÜNO-Symposium has as a goal to promote dialogue results and options for action for sustainable coastal management.

This survey is in preparation for the session "Options for Action - Science contributions to ocean and coastal missions" (Thursday, 13:45). We would like to better understand how your scientific work and/or engagement is contributing to goals articulated in the EU Mission "Restore our Oceans and Waters by 2030".

Join us in the session "Options for Action" to see and discuss the results of this survey!

Please note: All of your information will be anonymous and used for discussion purposes only.

To which of these three policy objectives does your work contribute?

Protection and restoration of marine and coastal ecosystems.

Prevention and elimination of plastic, nutrient and chemical pollution.

Multi-use of marine space in a sustainable and carbon neutral manner.

What do you think is the role of scientists in implementing these policy objectives?

Please complete the following sentence with the answers below. Multiple answers are possible.

Do you think scientists should ... :

... describe and/or understand the state of the ocean and coasts.

... give advice on the current and/or future state of the ocean and coasts based on the best available knowledge.

... join societal actors in protecting the ocean and coasts based on the best available knowledge.

... work with industry to maximise jobs and economic development in the ocean and coasts based on the best available knowledge.

... fully integrating understanding and action into research projects.

Options for Action - Restoration Project Design

The Challenge

A multinational offshore wind farm operator is seeking to develop a coastal area for a new wind farm. As a compensation measure, an equally large area adjacent to the wind farm is to be renaturalized. It is planned to guide the design of both the wind farm and renaturation area through scientific projects.

The Task

What could a scientific contribution to the restoration effort and the wind farm design look like?

Create a short title/acronym for your post.

Please use 5 characters maximum.

To which of these three policy objectives do you contribute?

Protection and restoration of marine and coastal ecosystems.

Prevention and elimination of plastic, nutrient and chemical pollution.

Multi use of marine space in a sustainable and carbon neutral manner.

At what point in the process does your contribution come into play?

Scientific foundation building

Providing advice

Co-designing

Co-implementing

Evaluating

List three keywords that characterize the contribution.

Please use commas to separate words.

